
Short Term Effect Of Home Based Exercises On Sedentary Activity Level And Anthropometric Measures In Young Adults- A Pre And Post Experimental Design

Vurelly Sneha¹

BPT student, Department of Physiotherapy,
School of Allied and Healthcare Sciences,
Malla Reddy University, Hyderabad.

Dr. Mubeena Banu.N²

Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy,
School of Allied and Healthcare Sciences,
Malla Reddy University, Hyderabad.

Dr. Mohammed Rafi³

Dean, Department of Physiotherapy,
School of Allied and Healthcare Sciences,
Malla Reddy University, Hyderabad.

Dr. Sowjanya Maruboyina⁴

Professor and Head of Department,
Department of Physiotherapy,
School of Allied and Healthcare Sciences,
Malla Reddy University, Hyderabad.

Email - mubeena_banun@mallareddyuniversity.ac.in

Received: 04th Jul. 2025

Revised: 13th Aug. 2025

Accepted: 22nd Aug. 2025

ABSTRACT

Background: Sedentary lifestyle and physical inactivity are global public health concerns contributing to obesity and other lifestyle disorders. Home-based exercise programs may offer a feasible solution. The aim of this study is to establish the short-term effect of Home-based exercise program on Physical activity level and Sedentary Behaviour pattern in young adults.

Objective: The aim of this study is to evaluate the Short-Term Effect of Home-Based Exercises on Sedentary Activity Level and Anthropometric Measures in Young Adults.

Materials and Methodology: A pre-post experimental study was conducted on 20 young adults (aged 18–25). Participants followed a 2-week home-based program combining aerobic and resistance exercises. The Anthropometric measurements assessed were Body Mass Index (BMI) and Waist Hip Ratio (WHR). Sedentary behaviour was assessed using the Sedentary Behaviour Questionnaire (SBQ). Data were analysed using SPSS v30 with paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests where appropriate.

Results and Discussion: The SBQ scores showed significant improvement post-intervention ($p < 0.001$). No significant changes were found in BMI ($SE = 14.147$, $p = 0.396$) and WHR ($SE = 0.500$, $p = 0.317$). Despite no statistically significant changes in BMI and WHR during the short intervention, the study effectively demonstrated notable improvements in sedentary behavior via SBQ (Mean=6.59, SD=3.42). Thus, this study suggests that short-term behavioral changes can effectively serve as catalysts for achieving broader health benefits, underscoring the critical need to incorporate sedentary behavior assessments into public health initiatives.

Conclusion: Short-term home-based exercises effectively reduce sedentary behavior in young adults but do not significantly affect BMI or WHR over two weeks. Future long-term studies are recommended.

Keywords: BMI, Home-based exercise, Physical activity, Sedentary behavior, WHR

INTRODUCTION

Global public health concerns have been significantly exacerbated by the growing prevalence of sedentary lifestyles. Societal transformations have contributed to reduced physical activity across various daily life aspects, negatively influencing overall health. The origins of this research date back to 1953 when Morris et al. observed that more than physically active workers exhibited lower risks of cardiovascular diseases. However, inconsistencies emerged over time regarding the definitions of sedentary behavior and physical inactivity. To address this, the Sedentary Behavior Research Network [SBRN] standardized these terms in 2012: "Sedentary behavior refers to any waking activity with energy expenditure less than 1.5 METs while sitting or reclining"¹³, whereas physical inactivity means not meeting the recommended physical activity guidelines.¹⁷

The World Health Organization updated its recommendations on physical activity and sedentary behavior. It is recommended that adults should engage in 150-300 minutes of moderate intensity or 75-150 minutes of vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity weekly, along with muscle strengthening activities¹⁴. Increased hazards of chronic health conditions have been strongly associated with prolonged sedentary behavior. Specifically, it is associated with a 112% higher risk of diabetes, 147% increased risk of cardiovascular disease, 90% increased cardiovascular mortality and 49% rise in all-cause mortality.²²

A systematic review found that sedentary behavior (SB), particularly TV viewing, has a weak correlation ($r=0.3$) with moderate to vigorous physical activity (MVPA), indicating that SB is an independent health risk factor regardless of overall physical activity levels.⁵ University-based studies exploring the impact of SB on body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (WC), and MVPA also demonstrated significant levels of sedentary behavior, highlighting that being active does not necessarily eliminate sedentary habits.¹⁸

Sedentary lifestyles have been extensively explored in efforts to address them. A systematic review highlighted various methods designed to reduce sedentary behavior (SB) in

adults, which included lifestyle modifications over a period of three to six months, aerobic and resistance training, as well as combined approaches that target both physical activity and SB.¹⁵ During the COVID-19 pandemic, attention was directed towards solutions that could be implemented at home. Evaluations showed that interventions, whether using a single approach or a combination of methods, that focused on strength, flexibility, balance, and endurance were beneficial for older individuals. Additionally, these interventions were utilized to improve mental health outcomes like anxiety and depression through the incorporation of tailor-made exercise regimen.⁶

Technology-based approaches to reducing SB have also emerged. Two studies utilized the Gruve solution—a wearable activity tracker with goal setting features—to decrease sedentary time over a 4-week period. Both studies reported favorable results, and one additionally used the Wellness Evaluation of Lifestyle scale to assess broader health aspects, including mental, spiritual, and physical well-being.^{2,3} Recent studies have broadened their horizons from solely concentrating on physical health benefits to including cognitive, emotional and mental well-being. For example, one study indicated that reducing sedentary behavior (SB) and increasing physical activity (PA) correlated with better executive function, particularly in terms of improved processing speed and working memory¹². Likewise, another study employed Square Stepping Exercise (SSE) to enhance cognitive and social abilities in inactive young adults¹⁰, with this program later expanded to encompass older adults in a follow-up study carried out in 2024 due to promising results. Although home-based exercise programs showed potential during the pandemic, similar initiatives in non-pandemic settings have been scarce. Importantly, a randomized controlled trial (RCT) implementing YouTube-based exercises for young adults over 12 weeks resulted in statistically significant advances in moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA), sleep quality and the frequency of muscle-strengthening activities ($p=0.00-0.002$).²³ Multiple studies have also focused on groups.

For instance, two studies were targeted at people with type 2 diabetes mellitus, with the goal of improving their physical activity levels,^{7,4} whereas another randomized controlled trial aimed at office employees.⁸ The latter included features of occupational ergonomics, height-adjustable desks, which notably lowered sedentary behavior in comparison to the control group.

In summary, sedentary behavior poses a unique and considerable health threat, separate from levels of physical activity. Approaches to combat sedentary behavior are varied, including changes in lifestyle, home-based exercises, digital solutions, and ergonomic improvements in workplace. Nevertheless, despite the existence of effective interventions, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, there is still a critical need for more comprehensive and sustained efforts aimed at addressing sedentary lifestyles in everyday circumstances. These interventions not only enhance physical health but also have significant consequences for mental and cognitive wellness. Thus, the aim of the study is to evaluate the Effect of Home-Based Exercises on Physical Activity Level and Sedentary Lifestyle in Young Adults.

AIM

The aim of this study is to evaluate the Short-Term Effect of Home-Based Exercises on Sedentary Activity Level and Anthropometric Measures in Young Adults.

OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate the effect of Home-Based Exercises on the Sedentary Activity Level in Young Adults
2. To evaluate the effect of Anthropometric Measures like Body Mass Index and Waist Hip Ratio in our target population

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The impact of a structured home-based exercise intervention on young people's physical activity and sedentary behavior was evaluated using a pre-post experimental design.

Ethical Consideration: The Ethical Committee of the School of Allied and Healthcare sciences at Malla Reddy University's granted ethical approval (**Ref No:**

ISC-SOAHs-PT/2025/089) on 28th of February 2025. Over the course of two months, an investigation was carried out.

Participants: A total of 20 individuals, 15 female and 5 male, aged 18 to 25, were selected from the university campus using non-probability convenience sampling. The participants' eligibility was evaluated based on the following criteria:

The criteria for participation include being between the ages of 18 and 25, leading a sedentary lifestyle (more than six hours of sitting each day), using screens excessively (TV, music, telephones), and being ready to participate and give informed consent. The participants were screened through the International Physical Activity Questionnaire-Short Form (IPAQ-SF)

Outcome Measures:

1. Sedentary Behavior Questionnaire (SBQ):

A validated self-reported tool assessing time spent in 9 sedentary behaviors

2. Body Mass Index (BMI): Calculated as weight (kg) divided by height squared (m²), Used to classify underweight, normal, overweight, and obese status

3. Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR): Ratio of waist circumference to hip circumference, Assesses fat distribution and risk of metabolic diseases.

Baseline and post-intervention values for all outcomes were recorded.

Data Collection: The data was obtained from young college adults of Malla Reddy University via circulating Google forms; therefore, potential participants were taken through primary screening of inclusion and exclusion criteria. A secondary screening was performed by asking them to fill out sedentary behavior and International Physical Activity Questionnaires. Based on their sedentary time and physical activity levels final participants are taken into the study.

Intervention: Participants completed a 2-week home-based exercise routine aimed at increasing physical activity and decreasing sedentary time. The regimen consisted of both aerobic and resistance exercise training.

Aerobic Component:

- 5-minute warm up walk at a comfortable pace.
- 15-minute cool down walk post-exercise.

Resistance component: Participants performed the following exercises:

Lunge-Place foot in front of the other, about an arm's length apart, while standing upright and keeping your feet hip-width apart. Lower your hips and contract your abdomen until both knees are 90 degrees off the ground.

Figure: 1 Lunge

Plank-Keep your arms shoulder-width apart and place your hands on the floor beneath your shoulders. Toes should be placed hip-width apart on the ground to form a powerful, straight line from head to toe.

Figure: 2 Plank

Side plank-Align the wrist and shoulder with one hand on the floor. With the knees straight and the feet stacked, the head and heel make a straight alignment, and the middle finger points forward.

Figure: 3 Side plank

Push-up- Arms shoulder-width apart, place hands on floor, aligned under shoulders. Lower your body by bending the arms while keeping the back flat and head slightly extended, until almost complete flexion. Return to the starting position with alignment.

Figure: 4 Push up

Squat- Place feet a little wider than shoulder-width and toes slightly outward. Bend hips backwards, while knees stay above the feet always. Unbend by pushing hips up without hyper-tension of the knees.

Figure: 5 Squat

Towel row- Standing up straight, with feet shoulder-width apart, strongly stretch towel outward, with elbows completely unbent. Bring towel close to chest while keeping the strong pull then return by unbending elbows, always keeping the stretch on the towel.

Figure: 6.1 Towel Row

Figure: 6.2 Bring Towel to your Chest

Back bridge- Lying down on your back, with hands on sides, knees bent, and feet at shoulder width apart. Make sure knees are bent properly. Push slowly on heels to lift hips off the floor while keeping your back straight. Return slowly to the starting position.

Figure: 7 Back bridge

Initially, each exercise was demonstrated to the participants with proper posture and technique via video call using the Google Meet Application, were asked to perform 4 sets of 15 repetitions. The exercise duration of each session was 60 minutes on all the days a week for 2 weeks. Adherence to the program was tracked via daily self-reported logs and weekly check-in texts through the WhatsApp group.

Data Analysis:

For data analysis, SPSS version 30 is utilized. For normalcy, the Shapiro-Wilk test was done. Signed-rank Wilcoxon test for the analysis of non-parametric variables (WHR, BMI) and the parametric variable (SBQ) was analyzed with paired t-test.

RESULTS

Table 1: Gender Frequency of the Samples

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	15	75.0
Male	5	25.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 2: Baseline Parameters of the Samples Including Age, Height and Weight

Variable	Sample size	Mean	SD	P-value
Age	20	21.450	1.4681	.012
Height	20	163.200	9.1514	.035
Weight	20	56.020	16.4697	.001

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Baseline Parameters Including BMI, WHR and SBQ

Variable	Mean	Median	Variance	SD
BMI	21.265	19.800	23.71	4.87
WHR	0.7995	0.7450	0.026	0.16
SBQ	21.9315	20.1500	147.2	12.13

SD-standard deviation, SE-standard error, BMI-Body mass index, WHR-Waist Hip Ratio, SBQ-sedentary behaviour questionnaire.

(Table 1) The study was conducted on 20 participants, with a majority being female (75%) and the remaining male (25%). (Table 2&3) The mean age of the participants was 21.45 years and shows baseline measurements showed a mean BMI of 21.265, a WHR of 0.7995, and an SBQ score of 21.9315.

Figure 1: Gender Distribution Ratio of participants

Table 4: Test of Normality for Age, Weight, Height, BMI, WHR and SBQ

Variable	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	P-value
Age	.870	20	.012
Weight	.794	20	.001
Height	.896	20	.035
BMI	.796	20	.001
WHR	.669	20	.000
SBQ	.925	20	.124

According to normality tests, SBQ scores were normally distributed, but Age, Weight, Height, BMI and WHR did not. Following the intervention, there was no statistically significant change in either WHR ($p=0.317$) or BMI ($p=0.396$), according to non-parametric tests (Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test).

Table 5: Within Group Analysis of BMI and WHR With Non-Parametric Test Wilcoxon's Signed Rank Test

Variables	N	Statistics	SE	STD. Statistic	Asymptotic
BMI PRE-POST	20	33.500	14.147	-.848	.396
WHRPRE-POST	20	.000	.500	-1.000	.317

N-sample, SE-standard error, BMI-Body mass index, WHR-Waist Hip Ratio

(Table 5) shows BMI: No significant change ($p = 0.396$), WHR: No significant change ($p = 0.317$) This suggests that the intervention was effective in improving sedentary behaviour related patterns among the participants.

Figure 2: Pre-Post Analysis of WHR and BMI within the sample group

Table 6: Within Group Analysis Of SBQ With Parametric Test Paired T-Test

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value
SBQ PRE-POST	20	6.59	3.41759	8.622	.001*

N-sample, SD-standard deviation, t-paired t-test value, SBQ-sedentary behavior questionnaire

* Shows significance at the level of $p < 0.05$

(Table:6) This table shows that parametric paired sample t-test demonstrated a highly significant reduction in SBQ scores after the intervention ($p < 0.001$), with a strong correlation ($r = 0.982$). SBQ: Significant improvement post-intervention (mean difference = 6.59, $p < 0.001$). Thus, while BMI and WHR did not show notable changes, there was a significant and meaningful improvement in sedentary behavior based on SBQ scores.

Figure 3: Pre-Post Analysis of SBQ within the sample group

DISCUSSION

The current study investigated the effects of structured lifestyle intervention on young adults Body Mass Index (BMI), Waist Hip Ratio (WHR) and sedentary behavior. These metrics were chosen as key indicators of

physical health and daily behavioral patterns, areas significantly affected by the rise in physical inactivity and sedentary lifestyles observed during and following the COVID-19 pandemic 13. Our objective was to determine if a short-term intervention could lead to substantial improvements in these crucial

parameters during daily routine timeframe in university students.

Body Mass Index

Although there was a slight numerical design, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, which was used to calculate BMI, showed no statistically significant difference between pre-and post-intervention scores ($p=0.396$). The findings are consistent with the research conducted by Ferreira Silva et al ²⁴ and McDonough et al. ¹⁶, which determined that short-duration or remote interventions did not significantly impact BMI. Although physical activity is crucial for long-term weight management, these findings suggest that it may not suffice to influence BMI in the short term, particularly in the absence of dietary modifications or increased activity levels. This is further corroborated by the WHO 2020 guidelines ⁴, which advocate consistent and structured activity to mitigate the risks associated with obesity.

Waist Hip Ratio

The present study has shown no statistical difference, when evaluated using Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test (0.317) but indiscernible improvement in pre-post values is observed. This is corroborated by Edwards et al.

⁸ and Rosenberg et al. ¹⁹, who emphasize that alterations in abdominal fat often lag behavioral modifications. Interventions aimed at reducing sedentary behavior and increasing ambulatory activities have shown potential but typically necessitate consistent adherence over extended periods.

Sedentary Behavior Questionnaire

Contrastingly, the Sedentary Behavior Questionnaire (SBQ) demonstrated a highly significant improvement following the intervention ($p=0.000$), with mean scores decreasing from 21.93 to 15.34. This suggests that participants adopted healthier behavioral routines regarding sedentary habits. Prior literature provides robust support for these findings. Both Zhu et al. ²³ and sagayner et al. ⁴ indicate that even short structured physical activity programs can have a notable effect on sleep quality, decrease sedentary behavior and enhance psychological well-being.

In addition, Kurtze et al. ¹¹ and Rosenberg et

al. ¹⁹ validated the SBQ as a reliable instrument for assessing behavioral change, thereby emphasizing the importance of our results. Notably, the strong relationship between pre- and post- SBQ values ($r = 0.9820$) demonstrates the consistency and efficacy of the intervention. The intervention's achievements in this area suggest that behavioral metrics such as sedentary activity may act as early indicators of more extensive health improvements.

This research corresponds with Wilke et al. ²¹, who similarly found that virtual or home-based physical activity initiatives-particularly when maintained throughout lockdown or isolation-had a positive effect on health behaviors, even if changes in physical measurements occurred more gradually. This indicates the significance of engaging in behavior as a basis for upcoming improvements in physical health. Fortunately, enhancements in sedentary Patterns and a decrease in sedentary habits can also indirectly contribute to long-term reductions in BMI and WHR by influencing hormones, hunger and energy use. ^{7,18}

Despite no statistically significant changes in BMI and WHR during the short intervention, the study effectively demonstrated notable improvements in sedentary behavior via SBQ. This highlights a crucial distinction in intervention effects: while behavioral changes can manifest quickly, physiological markers like BMI and WHR often require more sustained and long-term approaches. Thus, this study suggests that short-term behavioral changes can effectively serve as catalysts for achieving broader health benefits, underscoring the critical need to incorporate sedentary behaviour assessments into public health initiatives.

CONCLUSION

Home-based exercise programs are effective for reducing sedentary behavior in the short term. They are feasible and low-cost interventions for physically inactive young adults. However, there were no short-term effects on BMI and WHR.

Limitations

There are many constraints on this study. The findings' application may be limited by the small sample size and short intervention

period. Participants were not often observed because the program was conducted at home, which would have affected their adherence as well as the precision of how they performed the exercises. Additionally, the absence of rewards or motivating techniques could have affected participants' engagement. There is a chance of reporting bias when using self-reported data on physical activity.

Future Scope of the Study

Long-term follow-up of 6–12 weeks, studies with a larger sample size, and a diverse sample including homemakers and women going through or having gone through menopause are all part of the study's future scope. Control by Randomization Blinding procedures should be used when conducting trials. The application of exercise adherence techniques and evidence-based objective outcome selection further advances the study's future scope.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The Author provides no conflict of Interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I express my gratitude to our Respected Dean Dr. Mohammed Rafi, Our HOD Dr. Sowjanya Maruboyina and my guide Dr. Mubeena Banu N (PT) for the guidance and support in publishing the study. I am also thankful to my parents, friends and participant for their consistent cooperation and encouragement throughout the project.

REFERENCES

1. Akksilp K, Müller-Riemenschneider F, Teerawattananon Y, Tan SS, Arj-Ong Vallibhakara S, Suwanwela N, et al. The association of physical activity and sedentary behaviour on health-related quality of life: a cross-sectional study from the physical activity at work (PAW) trial. *J Assoc Stud Sedent Behav.* 2023; 2:22. [doi: 10.1186/s44167-023-00031-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/s44167-023-00031-7).
2. Barwais FA, Cuddihy TF. Empowering sedentary adults to reduce sedentary behavior and increase physical activity levels and energy expenditure: a pilot study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2015;12(1):414–27. [doi: 10.3390/ijerph120100414](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph120100414)
3. Barwais FA, Cuddihy TF, Tomson LM. Physical activity, sedentary behavior and total wellness changes among sedentary adults: a 4-week randomized controlled trial. *Health Qual Life Outcomes.* 2013; 11:183. [doi: 10.1186/1477-7525-11-183](https://doi.org/10.1186/1477-7525-11-183)
4. Brazo-Sayavera J, López-Torres O, Martos-Bermúdez Á, Rodríguez-García L, González-Gross M, Guadalupe-Grau A. Effects of Power Training on Physical Activity, Sitting Time, Disability, and Quality of Life in Older Patients With Type 2 Diabetes During the COVID-19 Confinement. *J Phys Act Health.* 2021;18(6):660–8 [doi: 10.1123/jpah.2020-0489](https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2020-0489)
5. Bull FC, Al-Ansari SS, Biddle S, Borodulin K, Buman MP, Cardon G, et al. World Health Organization 2020 guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. *Br J Sports Med.* 2020;54(24):1451–62. [doi: 10.1136/bjsports-2020-102955](https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2020-102955)
6. Chaabene H, Prieske O, Herz M, Moran J, Höhne J, Kliegl R, et al. Home-based exercise programmes improve physical fitness of healthy older adults: A PRISMA-compliant systematic review and meta-analysis with relevance for COVID-19. *Ageing Res Rev.* 2021; 67:101265. [doi:10.1016/j.arr.2021.101265](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2021.101265).
7. Dunstan DW, Kingwell BA, Larsen R, Healy GN, Cerin E, Hamilton MT, et al. Breaking up prolonged sitting reduces postprandial glucose and insulin responses. *Diabetes Care.* 2012;35(5):976–83. [doi:10.2337/dc11-1931](https://doi.org/10.2337/dc11-1931).
8. Edwardson CL, Biddle SJH, Clemes SA, Davies MJ, Dunstan DW, Eborall H, et al. Effectiveness of an intervention for reducing sitting time and improving health in office workers: three arm cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMJ.* 2022;378: e069288. [doi: 10.1136/bmj-2021-069288](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2021-069288)

9. Ferreira Silva RM, Fonseca Terra L, da Silva Valadão Fernandes M, Noll PRES, de Almeida AA, NollM. Physical activity and sedentary behavior in high school students: a quasi-experimental study via smartphone during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Children* (Basel). 2023;10(3):479. [doi:10.3390/children10030479](https://doi.org/10.3390/children10030479)
10. Kawabata M, Gan SR, Goh G, Chan DW, Koh D, Yap CW, et al. Acute effects of Square Stepping Exercise on cognitive and social functions in sedentary young adults: a home-based online trial. *BMC Sports Sci Med Rehabil.* 2021; 13:82. [doi:10.1186/s13102-021-00309-w](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13102-021-00309-w)
11. Kurtze N, Rangul V, Hustvedt BE. Reliability and validity of the international physical activity questionnaire in the Nord-Trøndelag health study (HUNT) population of men. *BMC Med Res Methodol.* 2008;8:63. [doi:10.1186/1471-2288-8-63](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-8-63)
12. Liu J, Wei M, Li X, Yang Y, Chen Z, Guo Y, et al. Substitution of physical activity for sedentary behaviour contributes to executive function improvement among young adults: a longitudinal study. *BMC Public Health.* 2024; 24:3326. <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-024-20741-0>
13. Marconcin P, Zymbal V, Gouveia ÉR, Jones B, Marques A. Sedentary Behaviour: Definition, Determinants, Impacts on Health, and Current Recommendations [Internet]. In: *Sedentary Behaviour – A Contemporary View.* IntechOpen; 2021. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.100250>
14. Marshall SJ, Biddle SJ, Sallis JF, McKenzie TL, Conway TL. Clustering of sedentary behaviours and physical activity among youth: a cross-national study. *PediatrExerc Sci.* 2002;14(4):401–17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1123/pes.14.4.401>
15. Martin A, Fitzsimons C, Jepson R, Saunders DH, van der Ploeg HP, Teixeira PJ, et al. Interventions with potential to reduce sedentary time in adults: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br J Sports Med.* 2015;49(16):1056–63. [doi:10.1136/bjsports-2014-094524](https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2014-094524)
16. McDonough DJ, Helgeson MA, Liu W, Gao Z. Effects of a remote, YouTube-delivered exercise intervention on young adults' physical activity, sedentary behavior, and sleep during the COVID-19 pandemic: Randomized controlled trial. *J Sport Health Sci.* 2022;11(2):145–56. [doi:10.1016/j.jshs.2021.07.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2021.07.009)
17. Owen N, Healy GN, Matthews CE, Dunstan DW. Adults' sedentary behavior. *Am J Prev Med.* 2011;41(2):189–96. [doi:10.1097/JES.0b013e3181e373a2](https://doi.org/10.1097/JES.0b013e3181e373a2).
18. Peterson NE, Sirard JR, Kulbok PA, DeBoer MD, Erickson JM. Sedentary behavior and physical activity of young adult university students. *Res Nurs Health.* 2018;41(1):30–8. [doi:10.1002/nur.21845](https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.21845)
19. Rosenberg DE, Norman GJ, Wagner N, Patrick K, Calfas KJ, Sallis JF. Reliability and validity of the Sedentary Behavior Questionnaire (SBQ) for adults. *J Phys Act Health.* 2010;7(6):697–705. [doi:10.1123/jpah.7.6.697](https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.7.6.697).
20. Sandra DA, Olson JA, Pageaux B, Roy M. “Ready-to-use” two-week home exercise program targeting depressive symptoms: pilot study. *Front Psychiatry.* 2023;14:1202955. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychiatry/articles/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1202955/full>
21. Wilke J, Mohr L, Yuki G, Ungricht L, Vogt L, Hollander K, et al. Train at home, but not alone: a randomised controlled multicentre trial assessing the effects of live-streamed tele-exercise during COVID-19-related lockdowns. *Br J Sports Med.* 2022;56(11):667–75. [doi:10.1136/bjsports-2021-104994](https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2021-104994)

22. Wilmot EG, Edwardson CL, Achana FA, Davies MJ, Gorely T, Gray LJ, et al. Sedentary time in adults and the association with diabetes, cardiovascular disease and death: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetologia*. 2012;55(11):2895–905. [doi: 10.1007/s00125-012-2677-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-012-2677-z)
23. Zhai L, Zhang Y, Zhang D. Sedentary behaviour and the risk of depression: a meta-analysis. *Br J Sports Med*. 2015;49(11):705–9. [doi: 10.1136/bjsports-2014-093613](https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2014-093613)
24. Zocoler CA, Madureira D, Santana JO, Ramos CC, Marques LR, Witter C, et al. Short-term power exercises increase physical fitness in middle aged adults. *J Phys Educ Sport*. 2018;18(Suppl 2):182. [DOI:10.7752/jpes.2018.s2182](https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2018.s2182)